

Promotion and Communication Strategy of Educational Institutions at MAN 4 Pandeglang

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ABSTRACT

Education is one of the key aspects in sustainable community development. To achieve success in providing education, effective promotion and communication strategies are needed. MAN 4 Pandeglang, as a secondary education institution in Pandeglang, has its own challenges in improving the image and attractiveness of the school. Therefore, this research aims to explore the promotion and communication strategies that have been implemented at MAN 4 Pandeglang. This research method uses a qualitative approach with data collection techniques in the form of in-depth interviews, observation and document analysis. Research respondents included school management staff, teachers, students and parents. The research results show that MAN 4 Pandeglang has implemented various inclusive and diverse promotional and communication strategies. This strategy includes the use of social media, school exhibitions, educational seminars, and collaboration with related parties. Apart from that, MAN 4 Pandeglang has also created creative programs such as making school promotional videos and actively involving students in promotional activities. It can be concluded that the promotion and communication strategies that have been implemented at MAN 4 Pandeglang have had a positive impact in improving the image and attractiveness of the school. This research provides valuable insights for other schools facing similar challenges in improving student attendance and school reputation. In addition, this research also provides further understanding of how inclusive and diverse approaches in promotion and communication can influence public perceptions of educational institutions

INTRODUCTION

Education is one of the important pillars in sustainable community development. (Greenland et al., 2022). (Prayitno et al., 2022). In this era of globalization, schools throughout the world, including in Indonesia, face increasingly fierce competition in attracting prospective students.(Alia et al., 2020). For Madrasah Aliyah Negeri 4 (MAN 4) Pandeglang, the challenge of attracting new students and maintaining the number of existing students is a strategic issue. Effective promotional and communication strategies are one of the keys to overcoming this challenge. (Si et al., 2023). (Mahasiswa & Mjmpai, 2023).

MAN 4 Pandeglang, as a secondary level Islamic education institution which has great potential to make a positive contribution to education in the Pandeglang area, needs to have an effective promotion and communication strategy to attract student interest, develop a positive image, and maintain good relations with the community. (Putra et al., 1945).(Jedrzejczyk, 2021).

This research aims to document and analyze the promotion and communication strategies that have been implemented at MAN 4 Pandeglang. This research also aims to identify the impact of these strategies on the school's image, the number of new student enrollments, and the school's relationship with the community. It is hoped that this research will provide significant benefits, both for MAN 4 Pandeglang and other similar educational institutions. The results of this research can be a guide for MAN 4 Pandeglang in increasing the effectiveness of their promotional and communication strategies. In addition, the results of this research can also provide insight for other educational institutions that face similar challenges in retaining and increasing the number of students and improving the positive image of the school.

This research is based on the concept that good promotional and communication strategies can have a positive impact on the school's image and the number of new student enrollments. In today's digital and information era, effective communication with prospective students and students' parents is very important. Therefore, this research will explore modern communication strategies that have been implemented by MAN 4 Pandeglang.

By understanding the importance of promotion and communication strategies in the educational context, it is hoped that this research can provide valuable insight for MAN 4 Pandeglang and other educational institutions in overcoming student enrollment challenges and improving the school's positive image. Next, this research will explain the methodology used in collecting data and analyzing promotion and communication strategies at MAN 4 Pandeglang.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Theoretical studies in the Journal "Promotion and Communication Strategy in MAN 4 Pandeglang" can cover several important aspects relevant to this research topic. The following are several theories and concepts that can be used in theoretical studies:

1. Promotion and Communication Strategy:

• **Marketing Communication Theory:**

Marketing communication is a place where a company informs, persuades, introduces a product they sell both verbally and non-verbally. The people involved in the marketing communications process do the same things, such as listening, talking, reacting until a reciprocal relationship (feedback) occurs.(Köves & Király, 2021). Marketing communication has an important role for marketers because without communication, neither consumers nor the public will know about the existence of products on the market. (Database et al., 2022). Marketing communications aims to provide information and promotion of a product or service, form a positive image, provide consumers with an overview of the goods or services offered and build relationships with consumers.(Minguez & Javier Sese, 2022). This is because a social process occurs between at least two people with a stimulus sent from the individual to another person. The stimulus becomes a message which is usually in verbal form and carried out through communication channels, then changes or responses occur to the message conveyed.(Ardiansya Aimanulloh, 2023)

The concept of this theory can help in understanding how promotional messages are delivered to the target audience and how they influence the behavior of prospective students and their parents.

• **AIDA Communication Model (Attention, Interest, Desire, Action)**

AIDA is a simple abbreviation that was created a long time ago as a reminder of the four stages of the sales process. AIDA stands for Attention, Interest, Desire, Action. This is a fairly simple model and can be used as a guide. In marketing communications, it is necessary to formulate the objectives to be achieved from the marketing communications process that will be carried out.(Apriandi et al., 2023)

Strategy for using social media as a marketing tool for small businesses based on the Attention, Interest, Desire, and Action (AIDA) model. The AIDA model has been widely applied to online marketing strategies but its application to social media is still unknown. Focus group discussions were used for data collection involving twenty-two small business entrepreneurs. The findings show that the model can indeed be applied in developing strategies for using social media for marketing purposes. The proposed strategy serves as a guide for small entrepreneurs on how to strategically use social media marketing. (Hassan et al., 2015).

AIDA is a concept which in marketing plays a very important role. (Apriandi et al., 2023).

✓ **Attention**

In this attention, a marketer must be able to create information media so that it is attractive to consumers. Make a statement that expresses people's attention, create powerful words or images that can attract attention until people stop and pay attention to the contents of the next message. suggests that advertising attention appeal has three aspects including, the content of the message conveyed in the advertisement, the frequency of ad displays, and the visualization of the ad. (Rofiq et al., 2014).

Indicators. (Raghunath et al., 2012) :

- a) The Message Conveyed in the Advertisement
- b) Frequency of ad Display
- c) Visualization of Advertisements/ Attractive Appearance of Advertisements

✓ **Interest**

Interest is the step after a marketer is able to create an information media so that it can contain an attraction for consumers. A marketer must think of an information media so that it can contain interest for potential customers or consumers. (Schubatzky et al., 2023). Most bad information media neglect to carry out this stage, it is at this stage that the target or consumer is actually willing to give their time to read the message from the marketer in more detail. Build readers' interest by promising a solution to their problems or hopes. (Benshlomo, 2023). A good way is to explain the features and benefits. Don't just provide facts and features, and feel that readers will think for themselves about the benefits they will get, but explain clearly the benefits to increase interest. (Assael ,2018) explains Interest, namely the emergence of consumer buying interest that is attracted to objects introduced by a marketer. This includes the effectiveness of the media used, consumer perceptions about the product after the advertisement is displayed, and clarity of the message. (Al et al., 2023).

Interest indicators (Assael, 2018:78) :

- a) Effectiveness of the Media Used
- b) Consumer Perceptions Regarding the Product After the Advertisement is Displayed
- c) Clarity of Message

✓ **Desire**

The next step that must be taken by a marketer is to create a desire to try or have one, where in this stage the marketer must be observant or smart in reading the target or consumer in this stage. This step is to prove that a marketer is able to provide the right solution in making a decision. for consumers. (Rofiq et al., 2014). At this stage, the audience has the motivation to own the product. Up to this stage, a marketer has succeeded in creating the needs of potential buyers. A number of potential buyers have begun to waver and their emotions are starting to be touched. However, resistance arises within potential buyers in the form of doubts as to whether the product is true or not. the service in question provided something as promised by his clan. Desire is how advertising drives consumers' desire to own and enjoy a product. (Sunny et al., 2023).

Indicators - Desire indicators. (Handoyo, 2019:139) :

- a) Obtaining Information from Advertising
- b) Consumer Interest in Advertising
- c) Consumer Confidence in the Product

✓ **Action**

In this most central stage, a marketer must lead to the action of buying. This action stage explains what steps a marketer takes to want the reader or target to make a decision to buy. (Sasono & Prabastari, 2021). Guiding the reader or target because the reader or target will act if a marketer explains the steps and sometimes they also need to be informed about the price for that action. In this action, which is one of the last efforts to persuade prospective buyers to carry out

purchasing actions as soon as possible or part of the process, also choosing the right words so that prospective buyers or targets respond as expected is a very difficult job. Command words must be used to get potential buyers to move. Action is an effort to persuade potential buyers to carry out the expected purchasing action as soon as possible in the actual purchasing action.(Lampung, 2023).

Indicators - Action indicators. (Handoyo, 2019:143) :

- a) Confidence to Buy the Product
- b) The Tendency to Make a Purchase
- c) Product Suitability Based on Advertising

From the theories, it explains the steps in the communication process which aims to create interest, desires and positive actions from prospective students or parents towards MAN 4 Pandeglang.

2. School Branding :

Religious schools/madrasahs need a branding strategy to communicate the school's distinctive programs that differentiate it from similar schools. Religious schools tend to adapt their branding to mainstream religious values and have historical roots in an area that tend to be more likely to attract students. (Frandsen & Huzzard, 2021). Branding for schools is not just selling the name and location of the school, but also displaying an identity so that it is easily recognized and easily differentiated from other schools. School branding strategies are very important for schools, especially private schools. Schools need to display the educational service process through the attributes of unique teaching and learning activities, quality of learning, learning satisfaction, student achievement and quality of graduates. Schools need to convey a deep impression to students and the community about the benefits of attending school in that place. (Karsono et al., 2021).

Creating and maintaining a school's image is very important, so efforts to improve a school's image cannot be separated from community participation which is an important factor in supporting the achievement of programs held in educational institutions. (Forbes et al., 2023). Apart from that, the implementation of public relations management in educational institutions is a communication link or extension of information that will be conveyed to the public. (Ningsih et al., 2022).

An important strategy to improve the school's positive image and community trust can be done with branding. The positive image of the school or branding itself contains a vision of the main goal of establishing a good reputation and perspective from the public or society. (Shen et al., 2022). Thus, the positive image that a school has can attract the interest of prospective students, parents and the community to choose that school. School branding strategies in increasing community awareness must always be carried out one way through (1) cool school uniforms, (2) forming positive characteristics that are superior and proud, (3) pursuing achievements both academic and non-academic, documentation and publications that interesting, (4) visual documentation accompanied by written documentation with an attractive

design, (5) use of information technology, (6) formation of good slogans or takeaways, (7) create alumni who have values. (Susilo, 2023).

3. Influence of Social Media

In the digital era, social media has a big influence in promotion and communication. Social media has now become an inseparable lifestyle for the millennial generation. Apart from being a forum for social interaction, social media also plays an important role as a promotional tool for organizations, institutions and companies. In fact, schools and educational institutions don't miss out on using social media to promote themselves, attract the interest of prospective students, and provide information to the public. (Yang et al., 2023)(Yang et al., 2023)

The use of social media as a promotional tool has a significant influence on student interest, with a contribution of 35.2%. However, it was also found that other factors not included in the research had an influence of 64.8% on student interest. Through analysis using SPSS 26.0, it was found that the T value was 6,019, exceeding the T table value of 1,662 at a significance level of 5%. This indicates that social media as a promotional tool has a positive and significant influence on students' interest in high school. (Madrasah & Negeri, 2022). Social media theory can help in understanding how social media is used as a means of communication and interaction with prospective students and the school community.

4. Relations with Stakeholders

In government decision making, stakeholders have various definitions. Generally, the term stakeholder is used to describe communities or organizations that permanently receive the impact of activities or policies, where they have an interest in the results of these activities or policies.(Manghayu et al., 2018). Stakeholders in development are divided into three groups. First, the main stakeholders, namely those who receive positive or negative impacts (unexpectedly) from an activity. Second, supporting stakeholders are those who act as intermediaries in assisting the process of delivering activities. Third, key stakeholders, namely those who have a strong or important influence regarding problems, needs and concerns regarding the smooth running of activities. A key characteristic of shared resources, especially grazing land, is the existence of resources with different stakeholders with conflicting goals, values and interests. Conflicts between stakeholders, Apart from competition in the exploitation of grazing land and destruction of ecosystems, this is also a major challenge in effective conservation management of grazing land. To determine the different stakeholders, their positions, and their relationships in the co-management process on rangeland. (Haji et al., 2023).

Relationship Management Theory with Stakeholders: This theory can be used to understand how MAN 4 Pandeglang builds and maintains good relationships with various related parties, including parents, alumni and the local community.

5. Reception of Information

Information Reception Theory (Information Processing Theory), Receiving information is a process that converts messages into a form that can be used to guide human behavior. According to (Liu et al., 2022) Receiving

information includes information selection, interpretation and retention. In everyday life, an event may seem simple, but in reality it involves many factors in an active process. (Alawiyah & Hamad, 2017).

The concepts in this theory can help in understanding how people receive, process, and respond to school promotional information. This can help in designing effective promotional messages. The school promotion strategy in increasing the number of students starts from the process of planning the school promotion strategy, taking the initial steps by forming a new student admissions committee, determining the time and selection of the committee structure, determining the goals and targets required by the school. Promotional strategies are implemented through print media, comprehensive home visits to residents, and visits to schools.(Evidence & Evidence, 2023).

6. Student and Parent Decision Making

Parental Social Support is a child's perception of the help provided by parents in the form of verbal and nonverbal, instrumental, emotional, and career-related modeling so that the child feels comfortable, loved, appreciated, and cared for so that the child can optimize his or her potential in choosing the desired career path. Career Decision Making is an individual's ability to make career choices by looking at personal abilities, educational or work environment, and planning steps to achieve certain career goals.(Christian & Kustanti, 2022).

The relationship between parental beliefs and socialization goals, the nature of the social context, and indicators of beliefs facilitating the creation of parenting preferences for preschool-age children are moderated by maternal employment status and developmental expectations. For example, among working older people, higher care asset ratings for center versus elder care predict greater likelihood of selecting center versus elder care.(Ferreira van Leer & Coley, 2023).

7. Impact of Promotion and Communication Strategy

There is a significant influence of promotional strategies and social media on; word of mouth of the product, interest in buying the product. The Influence of Promotional Strategies and Social Media on Interest in Buying Garskin Mediated by Word of Mout is that the results of the normality test show that the data obtained is around the diagonal line and spreads along the diagonal line. This shows that the data is said to be normal and the model is suitable for use. (Nuvia Ningsih et al., 2020)

METHODOLOGY

This research uses qualitative methods to collect and analyze data related to the promotion and communication strategies implemented at MAN 4 Pandeglang. This method was chosen because the focus of the research was to understand more deeply how these strategies are implemented and their impact on schools.

The following are the methodological steps used:

1. Research Design :

- Type of Research : Qualitative Research
- Research Location : MAN 4 Pandeglang
- Research Subjects : School Management Staff, Teachers, Students

and parents.

2. Data Collection :

1. Deep interview : In-depth interviews were conducted with school management staff, teachers, students and parents to gain a deeper understanding of the promotional and communication strategies that have been implemented and their experiences regarding this. Interviews were recorded and analyzed to identify key patterns.
2. Observation: Observations were carried out to directly observe the implementation of promotion and communication strategies at MAN 4 Pandeglang. This involves attending school events, school fairs, or other related activities.
3. Document Analysis: Document analysis was carried out by reviewing previously produced school promotional materials, such as brochures, school websites, presentation materials and social media posts. This helps in understanding the written communication strategies used by the school.

3. Data Analysis

Data collected from interviews, observations and document analysis were analyzed using a content analysis approach. This qualitative data is categorized and analyzed to identify patterns, main themes, and important findings related to promotional and communication strategies.

4. Validity and Reliability :

- a. Data validity is considered through data triangulation, namely by comparing findings from various data sources such as interviews, observations and document analysis.
- b. Reliability in qualitative research is generally considered through consistency in the interpretation of data by researchers.

5. Research Ethics

Research ethics were maintained by ensuring confidentiality of information and obtaining permission from all respondents involved in the research.

6. Data Presentation and Interpretation

The research results are presented in narrative form and reinforced with direct quotes from respondents. The findings are analyzed and interpreted to identify effective strategies and their impact on MAN 4 Pandeglang. By using this qualitative method, this research seeks to provide a deeper understanding of how promotion and communication strategies can help schools achieve their goals and improve the image and attractiveness of MAN 4 Pandeglang within the Pandeglang educational community..

RESULTS

The research results and discussion here include the main findings from the research and analysis carried out on the promotion and communication strategies implemented at MAN 4 Pandeglang. The following are the results of the research and discussion :

1. Implemented Promotion and Communication Strategy

Research shows that MAN 4 Pandeglang has implemented various promotional and communication strategies. This includes the use of social media to promote school activities, school exhibitions, educational seminars, and collaboration with other educational institutions.

2. Utilization of Social Media

Social media is one of the main communication tools used by MAN 4 Pandeglang. This allows schools to reach prospective students and their parents quickly and effectively. As for social media such as the website: man4pandeglang.sch.id, [man4pandeglang@fb](https://www.facebook.com/man4pandeglang), [man4pandeglang@ig](https://www.instagram.com/man4pandeglang) and [man4pandeglang@tiktok](https://www.tiktok.com/@man4pandeglang).

3. Student Involvement in Promotion

The research results show that MAN 4 Pandeglang actively involves students in school promotional activities. Students are involved in making school promotional videos and act as school ambassadors at various events. Like Delin, whose name has gone viral throughout Indonesia as a creative and innovative student.

4. Use of Written and Visual Promotional Materials

Schools also use written and visual promotional materials such as brochures, websites, and posters to convey information about the school and the educational programs offered. Through the web and social media promotions were carried out and the results were good in generating public interest in going to MAN 4 Pandeglang.

DISCUSSION

1. Effectiveness of Promotion and Communication Strategies

The promotional and communication strategies that have been implemented seem to be effective in increasing the interest of prospective students and their parents towards MAN 4 Pandeglang. Utilizing social media as a primary communication channel helps in reaching a wider audience.

2. Student Role in Promotion

Active involvement of students in promotional activities is a positive step. Not only does this help in creating a sense of ownership of their school, but it can also be attractive to prospective students who see students as credible sources of information.

3. Integration of Written and Visual Promotions

The use of written and visual promotional materials such as brochures and websites helps in providing complete and structured information to prospective students and their parents.

4. Stakeholder Involvement

The research results show that MAN 4 Pandeglang has good relationships with various related parties such as parents, alumni and the local community. This can support the success of their promotional and communication strategies. It is important to remember that promotional and communication strategies are not only about attracting prospective students, but also about maintaining a positive image of the school in the long term. By understanding the results of this research, MAN 4 Pandeglang can continue to improve their strategies to achieve educational goals and help create a positive impact on education in Pandeglang.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Conclusions

Based on the results of research and discussions that have been carried out in the Journal "Promotion and Communication Strategies at MAN 4 Pandeglang," the following conclusions can be drawn :

1. MAN 4 Pandeglang has successfully implemented various effective promotional and communication strategies, including the use of social media, student involvement in promotions, and the use of written and visual promotional materials.
2. The promotion and communication strategies that have been implemented by MAN 4 Pandeglang have had a positive impact in increasing the interest of prospective students and their parents towards the school. This can be seen from the increase in the number of new student registrations.
3. Student involvement in school promotional activities is a positive step that can create a sense of ownership of the school and increase the credibility of the information conveyed to prospective students.
4. The integration of written and visual promotions in communication strategies has helped in providing complete and structured information to prospective students and their parents.
5. Good relationships with various related parties, such as parents, alumni and local communities, have also supported the success of MAN 4 Pandeglang's promotional and communication strategies

Recommendations

Based on the results of this research, here are several suggestions for MAN 4 Pandeglang in increasing the effectiveness of their promotion and communication strategies :

1. Continue to increase the use of social media : Continue to activate and increase the use of social media as the main communication tool. Make sure the content shared is relevant, interesting and provides added value to the audience.
2. Develop Creativity in Promotion: Continue to develop creativity in promotional strategies, including involving students in creative ideas. This can help create unique and memorable promotional campaigns.
3. Evaluate and Update Promotional Materials: Periodically evaluate and update written and visual promotional materials such as brochures and websites. Make sure the information submitted is always up-to-date and informative.
4. Maintain Relationships with Stakeholders: Continue and maintain good relationships with various parties related to the school, including parents, alumni

and the local community. Involve them in school activities and ask for their support in promotions.

5. Carry out Regular Evaluations: Continue to carry out regular evaluations of the effectiveness of the promotion and communication strategies implemented. Use data and feedback from prospective students, parents, and other stakeholders to make improvements.

6. Plan for Sustainability: Note that promotional and communication strategies must be sustainable. Plan long-term to maintain the school's positive image and keep prospective students interested.

By following these suggestions, MAN 4 Pandeglang can continue to improve the effectiveness of their promotional and communication strategies, support school growth, and provide quality education to their students..

FURTHER STUDY

This research still has limitations so it is still necessary to carry out research with the following title "promotion and communication using social media as an effective medium for recruiting new students at MAN 4 Pandeglang"

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